

Biosynthesis and Characterization of Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

Biological synthesis of nanoparticles has emerged as rapidly developing research area in nanotechnology across the globe with various biological entities being employed in production of nanoparticles constantly forming an impute alternative for conventional methods. Simple prokaryotes to complex eukaryotic organisms including higher plants are used for the fabrication of nanoparticles. Techniques such as Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), Electron Microscopy (TEM, SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Energy Dispersive X Ray Spectroscopy (EDS) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) are used to elucidate the morphology, elemental composition and crystal structure of biosynthesized nanoparticles.

Keywords: Biosynthesis; Characterization; Nanoparticles

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is the study of manipulating matter on an atomic and molecular scale. Generally, nanotechnology deals with particles sizes between 1 and 100 nanometer in at least one dimension [1]. Quantum mechanical effects are very important at this scale, which is in the quantum realm. Nanotechnology is very diverse, ranging from extensions of conventional device physics to completely new approaches based upon molecular self-assembly, from developing new materials with dimensions on the nanoscale to investigating whether we can directly control matter on the atomic scale.

The definition of nanotechnology is based on the prefix “nano” which is from the Greek word meaning “dwarf”. In more technical terms, the word “nano” means 10⁻⁹, or one billionth of something. For comparison, a virus is roughly 100 nanometres (nm) in size. The word nanotechnology is generally used when referring to materials with the size of 0.1 to 100 nanometres, however it is also inherent that these materials should display different properties from bulk (or micrometric and larger) materials as a result of their size [2]. These differences include physical strength, chemical reactivity, electrical conductance, magnetism, and optical effects.

Origin: Historical views of nanotechnology

The first use of the concepts found in 'nano-technology' (but pre-dating use of that name) was in "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom", a talk given by physicist Richard Feynman at an American Physical Society meeting at California Institute of Technology (Caltech) on December 29, 1959. The term "nanotechnology" was defined by Tokyo University of Science Professor Norio Taniguchi in a 1974 paper as follows: "Nano-technology" mainly consists of the processing of, separation, consolidation, and deformation of materials by one atom or by one molecule." In the 1980s the basic idea of this definition was explored in much more depth by Dr. K. Eric Drexler, who promoted the technological significance of nano-scale phenomena and devices through speeches and the books *Engines of Creation: The Coming Era of Nanotechnology* and *Nanosystems: Molecular Machinery, Manufacturing, and Computation*, and so the term acquired its current sense [3].

Fundamental concepts

Nanotechnology is the engineering of functional systems at the molecular scale. This covers both current work and concepts that are more advanced. In its original sense, nanotechnology refers to the projected ability to construct items from the bottom up, using techniques and tools being developed today to make complete, high performance products. One nanometer (nm) is one

billionth, or 10⁻⁹ meter [2]. By comparison, typical carbon-carbon bond lengths, or the spacing between these atoms in a molecule, are in the range 0.12–0.15 nm, and a DNA double-helix has a diameter around 2 nm. On the other hand, the smallest cellular life-forms, the bacteria of the genus mycoplasma, are around 200 nm in length.

Why Nanotechnology Approach-

Nanotechnology approach is used because of the following reason-

- i. High surface area and high reactivity
- ii. Effective catalyst of plant/microbial metabolism
- iii. Better penetration into the cell
- iv. Increased both plant and microbial activities
- v. Nanotechnology opened doors to new ways of identifying and quantifying biomolecules through use of nanosensors and nanopores
- vi. Nanotechnology offers the tools to understand and transform biosystem, strong impact on sub-cellular dynamics, regeneration mechanisms, genome description, food characterization.
- vii. A new platform for synthesis of effective chemicals and biodegradable, food preparation, sensors and control. Biosynthesis of nanoparticles.

The definition of nanotechnology does not include unintentionally produced nanomaterials, such as diesel exhaust particles or other friction or airborne combustion byproducts, or nanosized materials that occur naturally in the environment, such as viruses or volcanic ash. Information from incidentally formed or natural nanosized materials (such as ultrafine particulate matter) may aid in the understanding of intentionally produced nanomaterials. Intentionally produced nanomaterials are categorized as Carbon-based (hollow spheres, ellipsoids, and nanotubes), Metal-based (quantum dots, nanogold, nanosilver and metal oxides), Dendrimers (nanosized polymers) and Composites nanomaterials. The unique properties of these various types of intentionally produced nanomaterials give them novel electrical, catalytic, magnetic, mechanical, thermal, or imaging features that are highly desirable for applications in commercial, agricultural, medical, military, and environmental sectors. Nanoparticles are viewed as the fundamental building blocks of nanotechnology. They are the starting points for preparing many nanostructured materials and devices. Their synthesis is an important component of the rapidly growing research efforts in nanoscience and nanoengineering.

A series of general methods for the nanoparticle synthesis have now been developed. An essential feature of their synthesis is the preparation of particles of specified size and shape (at least, the scatter of sizes should be small, 5% ± 10%, and controllable). The shape control and the possibility of synthesis of anisotropic structures are especially important. There are two main approaches are used in nanotechnology- bottom-up and top down approach. In the "bottom-up" approach, materials and devices are built from molecular components which assemble themselves chemically by principles of molecular recognition. In the "top-down" approach, nano-objects are constructed from larger entities without atomic-level control [4].

Synthesis of nanoparticles with a range of compositions, sizes and shapes has been demonstrated by various physical, chemical and biological means. Some of the very successful physical and chemical methods for the synthesis of nanoparticles include laser

ablation, ion sputtering, solvothermal synthesis, chemical reduction, sol-gel, photo-irradiations, radiolysis, ultrasonication, spray pyrolysis, solvated metal atom dispersion, chemical vaporization, and electrochemical methods.

Drawback of "physical" approaches is enormous consumption of energy to maintain the high pressure and temperature used in the synthesis procedures. The traditional and most widely used methods for synthesis of metallic nanoparticles use wet-chemical procedures. A typical procedure involves growing nanoparticles in a liquid medium containing various reactants, in particular reducing agents e.g., sodium borohydride or potassium bitartrate or methoxy poly ethylene glycol and hydrazine. To prevent the agglomeration of metallic nanoparticles, a stabilizing agent such as sodium dodecyl benzyl sulfate or polyvinyl pyrrolidone is also added to the reaction mixture. Generally, the chemical methods are low-cost for high volume. However, their drawbacks include contamination from precursor chemicals, use of toxic solvents, and generation of hazardous by-products [5, 3]. Hence, there is an increasing need to develop high-yield, low cost, nontoxic, different chemical compositions, sizes, controlled monodispersity and environmentally benign procedures for synthesis of metallic nanoparticles [6, 7]. As a result, researchers in the field of nanoparticle synthesis and assembly have turned to biological systems for inspiration. A vast array of biological resources available in nature including plants and plant products, algae, fungi, yeast, bacteria, and viruses could be employed for synthesis of nanoparticles.

It is well known that many organisms can provide inorganic materials either intra or extra cellular. For example, unicellular organisms such as magnetotactic bacteria produce magnetite nanoparticles, and diatoms synthesize siliceous materials. Multicellular organisms produce hard inorganic-organic composite materials such as bones, shells, and spicules using inorganic materials to build a complex structure. These bio-minerals are composite materials and consist of an inorganic component and a special organic matrix i.e. proteins, lipids, or polysaccharides that controls the morphology of the inorganic compound. The surface layer bacteria produce gypsum and calcium carbonate layers. Even though many biotechnological applications such as the remediation of toxic metals employ microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi, such microorganisms are act as eco-friendly nanofactories [8, 9]. Processes devised by nature for the synthesis of inorganic materials on nano and micro length scales have contributed to the development of a relatively new and largely unexplored area of research based on the use of microbes in the biosynthesis of nanomaterials.

The use of fungi in the synthesis of nanoparticles is a relatively recent addition to the list of microorganisms. The use of fungi is potentially exciting since they secrete large amounts of enzymes and are simpler to deal with in the laboratory. However, the genetic manipulation of eukaryotic organisms as a means of over-expressing specific enzymes identified in nanomaterial synthesis would be much more difficult than that in prokaryotes. In addition to good monodispersity, nanoparticles with well defined dimensions can be obtained by using fungi. Since fungi are known to secrete much higher amounts of proteins in their extracellular surrounding, thus might have significantly higher productivity of nanoparticles in biosynthetic approach.

Biosynthesized nanoparticles were stabilized by the proteins and reducing agents secreted by the fungus. Further, the reduction

of metal ions and surface binding of the proteins to the nanoparticles did not compromise the tertiary structure of the proteins. Growth conditions play an important role during the production of nanoparticles while using the fungi cultures [4]. During gold nanoparticle synthesis, it was observed that when gold ions were incubated with the *Trichothecium* sp. biomass under stationary conditions led to the formation of extracellular nanoparticles, whereas under shaking conditions, this was resulted in the formation of intracellular gold nanoparticles [10]. These proteins were released into the medium under stationary conditions and did not release under shaking conditions.

Characterization of biosynthesized nanoparticles

Nanoparticle characterization is necessary to establish understanding and control of nanoparticle synthesis and applications [7]. Characterization is done by using a variety of different techniques, mainly drawn from materials science. Common techniques are Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), Electron Microscopy (TEM, SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Energy Dispersive X Ray Spectroscopy (EDS) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) etc.

Dynamic Light Scattering

Dynamic light scattering also known as photon correlation spectroscopy is a technique which can be used to determine the size distribution profile of small particles in suspension or polymers in solution. When light hits small particles the light scatters in all directions (Ray-light scattering) so long as the particles are small compared to the wavelength (below 250 nm). If the light source is a laser, and thus is monochromatic and coherent, then one observes a time-dependent fluctuation in the scattering intensity [11]. These fluctuations are due to the fact that the small molecules in solutions are undergoing Brownian motion and so the distance between the scatters in the solution is constantly changing with time. This scattered light then undergoes either constructive or destructive interference by the surrounding particles and within this intensity fluctuation, information is contained about the time scale of movement of the scatters.

DLS system measures particle size from 1 nanometer to 6 microns at concentrations up to 40% w/v. All DLS systems measure light scattering effects arising from the Brownian motion of particles in suspension. Particle size distribution analyzers based on measuring the phenomenon of Brownian motion can be broadly classified as being based on either autocorrelators or on power spectrums.

Zeta potential

The zeta potential of a system is a measure of charge stability and controls all particles-particle interactions within a suspension. Understanding zeta potential is of critical importance in controlling dispersion and determining the stability of a nanoparticle suspension, i.e. to what degree aggregation will occur over time. The zeta potential is the measure of the electric potential at the slip plane between the bound layer of diluents molecules surrounding the particle, and the bulk solution [7]. This can be closely linked to the particle's surface charge in simple systems but is also heavily dependent on the properties of the diluents solution. The level of zeta potential between -30 mV and +30 mV results in greater electro-static repulsion between the particles, minimizing aggregation/flocculation.

Transmission Electron Microscope-

TEM is a microscopy technique whereby a beam of electrons is transmitted through a specimen, interacting with the specimen as it passes through. An image is formed from the interaction of the electrons transmitted through the specimen; the image is magnified and focused onto an imaging device, such as a fluorescent screen, on a layer of photographic film, or to be detected by a sensor. TEMs are capable of imaging at a significantly higher resolution than light microscopes, owing to the small de Broglie wavelength of electrons. This enables the instrument's user to examine fine detail even as small as a single column of atoms, which is tens of thousands times smaller than the smallest resolvable object in a light microscope. For the confirmation of nanoparticle size and shape TEM measurements can be carried out using drop coating method in which a drop of solution containing nanoparticles was placed on the carbon coated copper grids and kept under vacuum desiccation for overnight before, loading them onto a specimen holder [12].

Scanning Electron Microscope

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was extremely useful for the determination of topology and observations of surfaces as they offer better resolution and depth of field than optical microscope. SEM is a type of electron microscope that images the sample surface by scanning it with a high-energy beam of electrons in a raster scan pattern. The electrons interact with the atoms that make up the sample producing signals that contain information about the sample's surface topography, composition and other properties such as electrical conductivity. The types of signals produced by an SEM include secondary electrons (SE), back-scattered electrons (BSE), characteristic X-rays, light (cathodoluminescence), specimen current and transmitted electrons [13].

Atomic Force Microscope

The AFM is one of the foremost tools for imaging, measuring, and manipulating matter at the nanoscale. The atomic force microscope (AFM) is ideally suited for characterizing nanoparticles. It offers the capability of 3D visualization and both qualitative and quantitative information on many physical properties including size, morphology, surface texture and roughness. Statistical information, including size, surface area, and volume distributions, can be determined as well [14]. A wide range of particle sizes can be characterized in the same scan, from 1 nanometer to 8 micrometers.

X-Ray Diffraction

X-ray diffraction or crystallography is a method of determining the arrangement of atoms within a crystal, in which a beam of X-rays strikes a crystal and diffracts into many specific directions. From the angles and intensities of these diffracted beams, three-dimensional picture of the density of electrons within the crystal can be produced [15].

Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy

Electron dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) used for the determination of elemental composition and purity of the sample by atom %. Characteristic X-rays are emitted when the electron beam removes an inner shell electron from the sample, causing to fill the shell and release energy [13]. These characteristic X-rays are used to identify the composition and measure the abundance of elements in the sample, technique may known as EDX spectroscopy.

X-Ray Fluorescence

X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) is a technique used for chemical analysis of materials. An X-Ray source is used to irradiate the specimen and to cause the elements in the specimen to emit (or fluoresce) their characteristic X-rays. A detection system (wave length dispersive) is used to measure the peaks of the emitted X-rays for qual/quant measurements of the elements and their amounts [13]. XRF is routinely used for the simultaneous determination of elemental composition and film thickness.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

Infrared spectroscopic analysis is used to determine the chemical functional groups in the sample. It is the absorption measurement of different IR frequencies by a sample positioned in the path of an IR beam. Different functional groups absorb characteristic frequencies of IR radiation. Using various sampling accessories, IR spectrometers can accept a wide range of sample types such as gases, liquids, and solids. Thus, IR spectroscopy is an important and popular tool for structural elucidation and compound identification [16]. At temperatures above absolute zero, all the atoms in molecules are in continuous vibration with respect to each other. When the frequency of a specific vibration is equal to the frequency of the IR radiation directed on the molecule, the molecule absorbs the radiation. Infrared radiation spans a section of the electromagnetic spectrum having wavenumbers from roughly 13,000 to 10 cm⁻¹, or wavelengths from 0.78 to 1000 μm. It is bound by the red end of the visible region at high frequencies and the microwave region at low frequencies. IR absorption positions are generally presented as either wavenumbers or wavelengths. Wavenumber defines the number of waves per unit length. Thus, wavenumbers are directly proportional to frequency, as well as the energy of the IR absorption. The wavenumber unit (cm⁻¹, reciprocal centimeter) is more commonly used in modern IR instruments that are linear in the cm⁻¹ scale. In the contrast, wavelengths are inversely proportional to frequencies and their associated energy. At present, the recommended unit of wavelength is μm (micrometers). IR absorption information is generally presented in the form of a spectrum with wavelength or wavenumber as the x-axis and absorption intensity or percent transmittance as the y-axis.

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